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Tandem and transition metal-free synthesis of novel benzoimidazo-quinazoline as highly selective Hg²⁺ sensors

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Abstract

A one-pot procedure for the synthesis of novel planar aza-heterocycles possessing good fluorescence potencies was described. These benzoimidazopyrimido[4,5-b]quinolone derivatives came from the reaction of 2-chloroquinoline-3-carboxaldehydes and 2-aminobenzimidazole using K₂CO₃ in DMF. The fluorescence study of these conjugated systems was also considered, which revealed that they have highly selective sensing of mercury. Consequently, to investigate another aspect of the reaction, a three-component reaction was developed by adding malononitrile to the aforementioned starting materials in the presence of L-proline under reflux condition in H₂O/EtOH to provide amino-quinolin-3-yl-dihydrobenzo-imidazo-pyrimidine-3-carbonitriles in good yields.

Keywords: One-pot synthesis, Transition metal-free, Fluorescent, 2-Aminobenzimidazole, 2-Aminobenzimidazole